

متصفحات العنكبوتية العالمية : دراسة تحليلية مقارنة

المستخلص:

Summary of the Study This study discusses the Web browsers which are the main gate for the Internet and its applications. The study deals with the most popular as well as the most used browsers at the global level. These five browsers are Internet explorer, Firefox, Opera, Safari and Google Chrome. The study aims at discussing the emergence and development of Web browsers and figuring out its architecture and mechanism. Moreover, the study aims at knowing the need of information institutions for browsers and conducting different practical tests on browsers of this study in order to determine the most secure browser, the quickest browser and the least browser in using memory. The researcher depends on the analytical descriptive method which guarantees the ability of the analysis, diagnosis and interpretation of phenomena. Moreover, the researcher uses the comparative method to know the similarities and differences aspects among browsers under study in an attempt to fulfill the objectives of this study. The study found a set of the results as the following: - The emergence of browsers was simple. It was represented in the appearance of Nexus as the first web browser in 1990 by Tim Berners. It was a web browser as well as an editor for its page at the same time. - The development and modernization movement among browsers led to a competition between the producing companies for these browsers and the beginning of the First Browser War which was between Netscape and Internet explorer. This war put an end for the Netscape which was the most famous browser. In addition to this, the Internet explorer becomes the crowned king at the browser market. As a result for the continuous competition among browsers, a new conflict raised between the Internet explorer from one side and Firefox, Opera, Safari and Google Chrome at the other side in a new attempt to control the global browser market in what is known as the Second Browser War which has not been resolved till now. - There is a set of the main sub-systems which consists the architecture of the web browsers. They are represented in the particular sub-systems of interface, browser engine, the rendering engine, networking, JavaScript interpreter, Extensible Markup Language (XML) parser, display backend, and the data persistence in which the functions of these sub-systems were integrated together to fulfill the main goal of the browser which is the navigation via the web. - Information institutions are in need for browsers because these institutions use the Internet and the world wide web as browsers are the main gate for the Internet and all information services depend on the Internet. - The Opera browser in the position of turbo is the quickest web browser in the study. - The Firefox browser uses the least memory. - The Internet explorer is the most secure browser among the browsers of the study. In the light of the above results, the recommendations of the study are the following: - The use of Opera browser in the position of turbo in case of the slow communication networks because it is the quickest browser among browsers. - The use of Firefox in case of the low configurations computers from the technical aspect related to the hardware as the study found that Firefox was the least browser that uses the memory among the browsers of the study. - The use of Internet explorer because it is the most secure browser among the browsers of the study in case of there are strong systems for security and the need for secure browser. - It is recommended that similar studies will be conducted on the new issued versions of browsers. This is because the permanent competition and conflict among those browsers lead to new techniques which deserve study. Besides, different tests on the new browsers and new versions of browsers under study should be conducted in order to figure out the best of these browsers in term of speed, security and use of memory.